

**THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND TOOLS IN PATRIOTIC
EDUCATION OF STUDENTS****Teshaboyev Alikhoja Ibragimovich**

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ABSTRACT: This article talks about the role of pedagogical methods and tools in educating students in the spirit of patriotism, moral requirements for the pedagogue, and the attitude of the pedagogue towards the students.

KEY WORDS: nobility and patriotism, kindness, benevolence, professional pedagogical attitude, psychological path

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogues must educate students to have a sense of nobility and patriotism. Highness and patriotism are a special state of the soul. This state is formed by the combination of feelings of calmness, respect, love and pride in a person. The feeling of nobility and patriotism helps each person to make a correct assessment of himself by being educated from a young age. This quality is necessary for every person, but it is a necessity for a pedagogue. Because only a noble and patriotic person can awaken and develop this quality in demands. How can a person who has no self-respect teach others to respect themselves.

Only a person with inner awakening can bring harmony to the life of others. A noble and patriotic person rejoices at the success of others and suffers from their defeat. The teacher is not only happy with the achievements of the students, but also enjoys it. Because the pedagogue has a small share in this achievement. Defeat is also the defeat of the pedagogue.

The first moral requirement for a teacher is to look at the student with respect and love. Spiritual formation requires a lot of effort and a lot of time from the student. Internal contradictions can cause negative manifestations in the student's behavior. In such cases, the coach must act with kindness and tolerance within the bounds of etiquette. When evaluating each person, the coach should evaluate not based on his place in the team, academic success, parentage, but based on the level of formation of the student's inner world, his humanity. This non-discrimination should be treated with respect and try to eliminate defects while working on their education.

MAIN PART

The attitude of the pedagogue towards the students should consist of kindness, benevolence and help. It is known that development assistance is a complex process, and pedagogues who come to the conclusion that it is enough to put students in front of them and watch from the sidelines and only monitor how they fulfill these requirements, make a big mistake. It is not difficult to make a request, but it is difficult to achieve its fulfillment, so it is necessary to recognize that only a pedagogue who fully meets the requirements is a master of his profession. A good pedagogue should approach each requirement individually, carefully study what difficulties arise in meeting their requirements, what troubles them. He should benevolently help the student in this process.

In the work of the pedagogue, his emotional mood plays an important role at various stages of treatment: in the process of preparing for the activity, during its implementation, in the feelings and experiences felt after the relationship is realized. In this way, we are getting closer to the problem of managing the mental states of the pedagogue and their activity and attitude, which is very important for the implementation of professional pedagogical attitude.

In the process of professional pedagogical attitude, the problems of positive mood management are extremely important. It is a complex process to create and implement the psychological motivation for the lesson, the motivation for the relationship with the group, the inspiration for mutual exchange of ideas. Initially, based on the independent psychological behavior of the pedagogue, as a result of his attitude to the pedagogical work, as a result of his attitude to the material of the future activity that attracts him, based on the anticipation of his satisfaction with the relationship with the students, the inspiration arises during direct interaction with the group. It needs the same direct contact, develops and strengthens on the basis of direct interaction.

The creative mood of the teacher's relationship with students is a multifaceted process related to the uniqueness of the creative individuality of the teacher, the characteristics of the student group, working conditions, and so on. The mood of the teacher's attitude is largely related to the creative mood of the students, who are the subjects of pedagogical influence. Moreover, the creative mood that arises on the basis of the independent psychological behavior of the pedagogue depends on the relationship he has with the students during his organic cooperation with the group.

Before interacting with students, an important role is played by the pedagogue's desire to find external forms of expressing his emotional reaction to the educational material in advance: these are appropriate gestures, facial movements, tone of voice. Thinking of external forms of

expressing one's attitude to the educational material, of course, relies on such psychological preparation for the lesson, the event, that its components are listed. While reflecting on how to embody his thoughts and feelings better and brighter in the activities in the lesson, the pedagogue enters the situation of the future activity, concentrates on it, feels its forms, his emotional response to the activity looks for means to convey his attitude.

It is extremely important for a person to be able to control himself when dealing with students. The teacher's bad, uncreative mood in the lesson immediately affects the creative mood of the group as a whole, reduces the effectiveness of their joint activities. The proposed system of managing creative mood requires individual mastery, regular self-directed work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Management of creative mood in the process of dealing with students and immediately before it is the most important professional requirement of a pedagogue's work. In relation to the main stages of pedagogical creativity, the following aspects of the influence of treatment on the creative mood of the pedagogue can be distinguished:

- that the pedagogue's precognition of behavior in the group is a factor that mobilizes his creative mood;
- the initial contact with the group as a stimulating factor of the creative mood of the pedagogue during direct interaction;
- system of interaction of the pedagogue with the group:
- it supports and encourages the development of the creative mood of the pedagogue in the process of activity;
- creating satisfaction from treatment as a factor stimulating the creative mood of the pedagogue in the subsequent activity.

Pedagogical treatment process is complicated by a number of conditions. The conditions of dealing have a significant influence on the nature of dealing, in fact they largely determine the professional direction of dealing. The transparency of the transaction creates many difficulties. As the researchers noted, dealing in front of people, in front of a large audience, is extremely difficult for beginners and cannot be done without special preparation. Only acquiring the skills and methods of mutual exchange of ideas ensures the emotional mood of the pedagogue in the process of communication.

A particularly important treatment for managing the teacher's creative mood is to release and mobilize such a mood immediately before the activity, to overcome the uncreative mood, and etc.

The peculiarity of the implementation of the method of "physical actions" in the creativity of a pedagogue is that it is necessary for the pedagogue only as a means of mobilizing his creative nature before the beginning of direct creativity, and then "physical actions" in the "if" state are logical with the situation of creativity. slowly grows into a truly spiritual disposition, no longer in the "if" state, but in real dealings with the group.

Forming a creative mood in communication is a complex process. Here, the pedagogue often experiences a sense of tension, which is due to the activity of the pedagogue's creativity among the masses, the changing state of creativity, the need to manage his mental states operatively, the richness of the work in terms of mutual exchange of ideas. features require.

A pedagogue should strictly observe the teacher's etiquette while living in cooperation with students. He must not tell the secret of the student entrusted to him, not laugh at him, and be sincere with him.

CONCLUSION

Pedagogues must cultivate a sense of nobility and patriotism. Highness and patriotism are a special state of the soul. This state is formed by the combination of feelings of calmness, respect, love and pride in a person. The teacher's attitude towards the students should be kindness, benevolence and help. It is known that development assistance is a complex process, and pedagogues who come to the conclusion that it is enough to put students in front of them and watch from the sidelines and only monitor how they fulfill these requirements, make a big mistake.

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